

DEFINITIONS OF GEODIVERSITY, GEOHERITAGE, GEOSITE

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The following tables provide definitions of geodiversity, geoheritage, and geosite as collected from literature.

GEODIVERSITY	Brocx and Semeniuk (2007)	the natural variety of geological, geomorphological, pedological, hydrological features of a given area, from the purely static features (i.e., products such as shorelines, sandy spits, or limestone pinnacles, or river canyons) at one extreme, to the assemblage of products, and at the other, their formative processes (e.g., active parabolic dunes forming under a given wind regime) (After Semeniuk, 1997)
	Gray (2013)	The natural range (diversity) of geological (rocks, minerals, fossils), geomorphological (landforms, topography, physical processes), soil and hydrological features. It includes their assemblages, structures, systems, and contributions to landscapes

GEOHERITAGE	Brilha (2018)	Geoheritage, or geological heritage in its extended form, is materialized by exceptional elements of geodiversity , namely minerals, fossils, rocks, landforms and their landscapes, soils, and active geological and geomorphological processes.
	Brocx and Semeniuk (2007)	Globally, nationally, state-wide, to local features of geology, such as its igneous, metamorphic, sedimentary, stratigraphic, structural, geochemical, mineralogic, paleontological, geomorphic, pedologic, and hydrologic attributes, at all scales, that are intrinsically important sites, or culturally important sites, that offer information or insights into the formation or evolution of the Earth, or into the history of science, or that can be used for research, teaching, or reference. (After Semeniuk, 1997; Semeniuk and Semeniuk, 2001)
	Dong et al (2013)	Geoheritage refers to the existing geodiversity in a given place (Gray, 2004) with the idea is that as long as the heritage of geological sites is preserved, Earth's geodiversity will be sustained [...] The most efficient way to achieve geoconservation is to increase public awareness about the value of geoheritage sites (scientific, aesthetic, educational, tourism, economic, intrinsic) through promotion and interpretation via geotourism (Hose, 1995, 2008, 2012; Burek and Prosser, 2008; Hose and Vasiljevic, 2012)
	Georgousis (2021)	Geoheritage includes those elements of geodiversity that have scientific, educational, cultural, aesthetic, and ecological value for humans [Sharples 2002, Woo 2017]
	Gray (2018)	Geoheritage are those parts of the identified geodiversity of the earth that are deemed to be worthy of conservation because of their importance/value .
	Kubalikova (2013)	The concept of geoheritage is based on the definition of natural heritage which was presented already in 1972 (UNESCO, 1972). The term geoheritage was defined as those components of natural geodiversity of significant value to humans, including scientific research, education, aesthetics and inspiration, cultural development, and a sense of place experienced by communities (Dixon, 1996, p. 14). A similar definition is presented by Eberhard (1997); he emphasizes that geoheritage belongs to the "things we would wish to retain for present and future generations".
	NPS (https://www.nps.gov/subjects/geology/geologic-heritage-terms.htm)	Geologic Heritage encompasses the significant geologic features, landforms, and landscapes characteristic of our Nation which are preserved for the full range of values that society places on them, including scientific, aesthetic, cultural, ecosystem, educational, recreational, tourism, and other values. Geoheritage sites are conserved so that their lessons and beauty will remain as a legacy for future generations.
	Sharples (2002)	Geoheritage comprises those elements of natural geodiversity which are of significant value to humans for non-depleting purposes which do not decrease their intrinsic or ecological values

	Szepesi et al (2017)	the geological heritage (or geoheritage) and the geosites refer to particular types and locality of geodiversity elements that have acquired scientific, cultural/historical and or socio-economic value (Brocx and Semeniuk 2007; Reynard et al. 2007, 2015; Brilha 2016)
	Vasiljević et al (2011)	[...] Dixon (1996) who claims that only components of geodiversity that have significant value to humans, with scientific, educational, aesthetical and inspirational meaning can be considered as geoheritage. Furthermore, geoheritage is considered to be the concept that comprises existing cases of geodiversity, identified as having conservation significance (Gray, 2004)
	Vujičić (2011)	The components of geodiversity that have scientific, educational, aesthetical and inspirational significance are considered to be determined as geoheritage (Dixon 1996; Erhartič 2010) and they are identified as having conservation significance (Gray 2004, Erikstad 2008).

GEOSITE	Brilha (2018)	The in-situ occurrence of geodiversity elements with high scientific, educational, aesthetic, and cultural value is usually known as “geosite” - or “geomorphosite” if the valued element has a geomorphological nature (Reynard, 2005).
	García Cortés and Carcavilla (2013)	A Geosite, or Site of Geological Interest, is an “area that is part of the geological heritage of a natural region as constantly shows one or several characteristics that are considered significant in its geological history”
	Newsome and Dowling (2018)	Key localities of particular geological interest are termed geosites (Brilha, 2018).
	Wimbledon (1995)	Site location area or territory in which it is possible to identify a geological or geomorphological interest for conservation

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